

Reprocessing Thermoplastic Composite Trim Waste with High-Temperature Compression Moulding

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ICCM24

24TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

August 4-8, 2025 Baltimore Convention Center
- Baltimore, MD

Singapore Institute of Manufacturing Technology (SIMTech), A*STAR

Almost the furthest flight to ICCM

Singapore Institute of Manufacturing Technology

(5 Cleantech Loop, #01-01, CleanTech Two Block B, Singapore 63673)

MTI MINISTRY OF TRADE AND INDUSTRY SINGAPORE

a Agency for Science, Technology and Research SINGAPORE

a Singapore Institute of Manufacturing Technology SIMTech

A world-class innovation partner in advanced manufacturing technologies, systems and capabilities

- Founded in 1993
- SIMTech have 400+ staff, ~90 students

Manufacturing will be Smarter, Greener and More Connected in the Future

Next-Gen Manufacturing Processes

- 4D Additive Manufacturing
- Adaptive Machining & Surface Engineering
- Hybrid & Multi-Materials Forming
- MedTech Manufacturing
- Extreme Manufacturing
- **Advanced Polymer and Composite processing**

Autonomous Manufacturing

Enabling Data-Driven and Knowledge-Based Manufacturing with Workforce Augmentation Technologies

Polymer and Composite Processing Group @ SIMTech

01. Injection Moulding Process

02. Sheet Compression Moulding & Thermoforming

03. Extrusion and Additive Manufacturing

04. Lightweight Design and Process Simulation

- Vacuum Forming
- 2IR Composite Thermoforming
- Compression Moulding
- In-situ consolidation
- In-situ polymerization

□ Polymer Injection Moulding (Auburg Allrounder 570H, 200T, 2500bar, 450°C)

□ Injection Compression Moulding (Witmann Ecopower 110, 110T, 2100bar, 350°C)

□ High Temperature Extruder (Leistritz ZSE 27 MAXX, L/D ratio: 48, screw Diameter: 27mm, 450°C, melt pressure: 220 bar)

□ Integrated Composite Thermoforming (320T-1.2x1.2m 125kW 2IR)

□ Hot Press Sheet Consolidator (60T-40x40cm platen - 450°C, equipped with a water chiller)

□ Vacuum Thermoforming (Formech HD1500, 1.5x1m, x10mm, 55kW quartz heater)

□ Vacuum Thermoforming (CMS eidos se 1.5x1mx10mm, 75kW halogen heater)

□ Microinjection Moulding (Babyplast, 6T, 1850bar, 75x75x70mm mould)

□ Drying oven (Gen lab, 1.6x1.1m sheet size, 50 sheets 250°C)

□ Composites Curing Oven (OV301 - 1070x440x500mm - 200°C)

□ Portable Hot Bonder (Aerofom Composites AHB-380-s, 16 Amp or 32 Amp and 10 thermocouples)

Background

- **Forged composite molding (FMC)**, originally developed for compression molding of chopped carbon fiber-reinforced thermosets, is widely used in the automotive sector.
- With growing focus on sustainability and circularity, **thermoplastic molding compounds** are gaining traction.
- **Thermoplastic BMCs/SMCs** also offer benefits better fracture toughness and faster cycle times, though they require higher processing temperatures than thermosets.
- This study investigates the use of a **high-temperature compression moulding** unit for **reprocessing thermoplastic waste** via bulk moulding.

Mitsubishi CF thermoset SMC
[<https://www.m-chemical.co.jp/carbon-fiber/en/product/fmc/>]

GF thermoset SMC used to produce battery box
[https://teijin-mobility.com/en/new_tech/gf-smc/]

Toray chopped fiber thermoplastic BMCs
[<https://www.toraytac.com/products/thermoplastic/bulk-molding-compounds>]

What is LCF?

- Trim waste, known as **Loose Chip Forms (LCF)**, is generated during prepreg cutting and is repurposed into **uniform rectangular chips** for recycling.
- A **die cutter** is used to shape the chips into consistent sizes.
- The uniform chips are then **recycled using a compression moulding process**.
- This approach gives **a second life to the trim waste**, turning it into useful material.

Fabricated LCF
composite panel

LCFs of 5HS CF-PPS (Polyphenylene Sulfide)

Excess, waste material

Die Cutter

Uniform LCF

Shredder/Grinder

Non-uniform LCF

Thermal Characterization

- **Melting, crystallization** (from DSC) and **degradation temperature** (from TGA) data shows **processing window** whereby PPS can flow and allow forming of the prepreg without degradation onset.
- Higher % crystallinity: polymer crystals are hard and strong, which affects **mechanical properties**.

- Melting point: **289°C**; Crystallisation point: **251°C**;
Crystallinity: 45.3 (as received), 43.9 (after processing)

- Onset degradation temperature: **477°C** at 5% PPS loss; PPS content: 35.7 wt%.

Processing parameters	
Heating temperature	320°C – 330°C
Cooling rate	10°C/min (quench)
Pressure	12.5 bar – 15 bar

Tensile performance: Uniform vs Non-uniform LCF

Strength [MPa]

Modulus [GPa]

- Uniform LCF (random) outperforms non-uniform LCF by 49% in tensile strength.
- Non-uniform LCF shows no meaningful improvement over neat PPS in tensile strength.
- Uniform LCF achieves 15%, and non-uniform LCF only 10%, of the tensile strength of continuous CF-PPS.

- Non-uniform LCF shows a 6.5x improvement in tensile modulus over neat PPS, but is:
 - 30% lower than Uniform LCF
 - 47% lower than Continuous CF-PPS
- The lower tensile strength and modulus of **non-uniform LCF** is likely due to **more fiber fractures during the shredding process**, resulting in **shorter damaged fibers** that reduce reinforcement efficiency.

Failure of Uniform and Non-uniform LCF

Uniform LCF

Non-uniform LCF

- **Both uniform and non-uniform LCF composites** primarily failed at **the fiber-matrix interface**, indicating **matrix-dominated failure mechanisms**.
- This is supported by cross-sectional fracture images, which show poor debonding rather than fiber breakage.
- As a result, the overall tensile strength of these composites remains relatively close to that of neat PPS.

Efforts to Improve Mechanical Performance

1. Material Blending

- Added uniform LCF to PPS pellets with 30% short fibers.
- Aimed at increasing matrix-fiber interaction and strength.

2. Chip Arrangement (Ordered)

- Used overlapping and stacked configurations of LCF.
- Improved load transfer paths and reduced weak inter-chip interfaces.

3. Processing Parameter Enhancement

- Applied isothermal crystallization at 270°C during compression moulding.
- Targeted improved crystallinity and interfacial bonding for better mechanical integrity.

5HS CF-PPS (100g)
+ short fiber CF-PPS pellets (50g)

1. Blended with short fiber reinf. PPS pellets

2. Ordered

3. Processing parameters	Standard	Optimized
Heating temperature	320°C – 330°C	320°C – 330°C
Isothermal crystallization	-	270°C for 30 mins
Cooling rate	10°C/min	10°C/min
Pressure	12.5 bar – 15 bar	12.5 bar – 15 bar

- Manipulate crystallization process to promote larger crystal aggregates bridging between individual chips.
- This should allow for mechanically interconnected or interlocked the individual chips => stronger connection between the chips.
- Unlike method 2 (chip arrangement / ordered LCF), isothermal crystallization does not require additional time or automation for chip alignment.

Improvement on Tensile Properties

Compared to the Uniform LCF (Random):

- **Blending with short-fiber PPS pellets reduced both tensile strength and modulus**, reflecting limited fiber-matrix reinforcement and a more matrix-dominated structure due to reduced fiber content.
- **Aligning and stacking LCF chips enhanced tensile strength by 68% and modulus by 19%**, attributed to improved load transfer through better chip-to-chip connectivity.
- **Isothermal crystallization led to a moderate strength gain**, likely resulting from increased crystallinity.

Benchmarking against a Commercial Thermoset SMC

- SMC is commonly used for interior panels and cabin linings, including window surrounds, wall panels, galley modules, lavatory shells, and floor liners.

Aviation-certified glass-filled SMC
from Polynt composites
(HUP 27/25 RN-9010)

- All reprocessed LCF composites outperformed the commercial aviation-grade glass-filled SMC (60 MPa) in tensile strength demonstrating that even in their various forms, **reprocessed LCFs** offer superior mechanical performance and are **viable candidates for interior cabin applications**.

Conclusion

- **Non-uniform (shredded) LCF underperformed** compared to uniform LCF, with 30% lower tensile strength and modulus, likely due to fiber damage and shortened lengths.
- **Ordered LCF arrangement yielded the best mechanical enhancement**, achieving 2.6x higher tensile strength and 11x higher modulus than neat PPS, and reaching 26% of the tensile strength and 90% of the modulus of continuous CF-PPS.
- **The thermal processing (Isothermal crystallization) approach also showed a positive effect on the mechanical properties**, delivering 1.3x higher tensile strength than randomly aligned uniform LCF.
- **Material blending with short-fiber reinforced PPS pellets showed negligible improvement** in tensile properties.
- **The ability of reprocessed LCFs to meet or exceed the tensile strength of thermoset SMC highlights their potential for lightweight, recyclable thermoplastic alternatives** in aerospace interior applications, offering additional benefits in sustainability.

Future work

- Investigate the **effect of LCF size and aspect ratio** on mechanical performance.
- Evaluate **notch sensitivity** through open-hole tension (OHT) and open-hole compression (OHC) testing, benchmarking the results against neat PPS and continuous CF-PPS to assess damage tolerance and structural applicability.

ICCM25 – welcome to SG

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Marina_Bay_Sands#/media/File:Marina_Bay_Sands_in_the_evening_-_20101120.jpg

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gardens_by_the_Bay#/media/File:Supertree_Grove,_Gardens_by_the_Bay,_Singapore_-_20120712-02.jpg

https://www.tripadvisor.co.id/Attraction_Review-g294265-d644919-Reviews-Merlion_Park-Singapore.html

<https://www.visitsingapore.com/neighbourhood/featured/neighbourhood/marina-bay/singapore-flyer/>

PCP members

THANK YOU

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